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VIDIŚĀ AND ITS ENVIRONS IN EARLY MEDIEVAL INDIA: Research Group Working Paper 2002¹

Historiography of Early Medieval India

The early models for studying state and society in ancient India were not developed specifically to understand processes of change. Most instead sought to understand the characteristics and functioning of the early Indian state. Arguments about historical change only emerged by default. For a long time, Indian social and cultural historians worked according to the seemingly convenient categories of ‘ancient-medieval’ and ‘modern’ which had replaced the older communally and racially charged periodisation of Hindu-Muslim-British. The theories of change which emerged in much of this scholarship focused around the shift from more or less positively viewed ‘ancient’ societies and polities to more or less decadent ‘medieval’ ones. This shift from ancient to medieval India took the form of the fragmentation of the great imperial Mauryan and Gupta states into ever fissiparous petty regional kingdoms, the ossification of caste, the degeneration in art of more naturalistic classicism into highly fantastic and ornamental forms, the degeneration of religion into superstition, and the desiccation of philosophy into commentarial scholasticism. These characterisations were not so much historical arguments as explorations of national identity.

After independence more searching and critical evaluations of these problems were produced by historians and social scientists, many associated with leftist historiography. Marxists and non-Marxists alike shared the view that the ancient or ‘early historical’ state was characterised by a highly bureaucratic and centralised structure in which the remuneration of state servants was in cash. Urban development was pronounced and the economy was highly monetized, characterised by extensive craft production and long-distance foreign trade. The social basis of this highly urbanised economy was a varna system that had crystallised into a society where the brahmanas and kṣatriyas acted as appropriators of social surplus, vaiśyas as agriculturalists and merchants, and śūdras as providers of servile labour, often in the form of slavery or helotry. This ancient or ‘early historic’ complex gradually shifted in the Gupta period to an ‘early medieval’ or more aptly ‘feudal’ era. This new order witnessed a substantial contraction of long-distance trade, a decrease in money as a medium of exchange, the diminishment of artisanal commodity production, the decline of cities, and the economic isolation of the village – in short, the ‘closure of the Indian economy’. The most important development, however, was the growth of what scholars called a ‘land-grant economy’. As money was scarce, kings remunerated state servants and gave to religious beneficiaries in land, in each case parcelling out state power to local landed interests. This led to a fragmentation and decentralisation of political power, particularly through the emergence of a system of military vassalage among secular lords. Concomitant with this was the growth of a class of landed intermediaries. There was considerable caste proliferation at the lower end of the varna hierarchy, particularly among the sudras, who evolved into an impoverished and landless peasantry. Ideology and culture shifted from urbane classicism to ‘feudal’ courtly decadence on the one hand and a bhakti dominated theistic religion centred around the temple.

¹ Some of the ideas explored in this working paper reached formal publication in Daud Ali, “The historiography of the Medieval in South Asia,” *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 22, no. 1 (2012): 7–12, and Daud Ali, “The idea of the Medieval in the writing of South Asian history: contexts, methods and politics,” *Social History* 39, no. 3 (2014): 382–407.

The immense contribution of this historiography was to move the critical emphasis and scrutiny away from the dynastic state and instead onto the study of economy and society. The particular thesis of 'Indian feudalism', however, remained contentious, and was challenged on both theoretical and evidentiary grounds in debates revolving around the classification of the ancient Indian social order, modes of production, and alternative theories of state formation which continued in the 70s and 80s. While the outcome of these debates has not been decisive or shown a clear alternative, several empirical claims of the feudalist model have been seriously complicated if not outright refuted. John Deyell's work on the monetary history of north India, for example, argued that the demonetisation thesis was based on a sometimes careless and inappropriate methodology. In north India, the period between 600 and 1000 CE showed as high a number of coins in circulation as in Sātavāhana times. Similarly, the thesis of widespread urban decay had to be counterbalanced by the fact that while archaeology seemed to demonstrate that the great cities of early historic India did witness a marked contraction in size, there was also considerable urban growth, as new regional capitals and smaller urban settlements emerged across the subcontinent. This latter point was advanced in a series of studies working under the rubric of 'urbanisation', 'urbanism' and 'urban development'. During the 1980s and 1990s historians and anthropologists developed alternative models of the state which implicitly challenging both nationalist and to a lesser extent Marxist orthodoxy.

Perhaps most prominent among these studies was the work of B. D. Chattopadhyaya, whose influential articles precipitated a more widespread critique of earlier historiography, and embodied something of an alternative model. In the introduction to a collection of seminal articles, aptly titled *The Making of Early Medieval India*, Chattopadhyaya argues that historical processes in post-Gupta India should not be seen as a fragmentation, contraction, or decay -- in short, a disarticulation -- of early historic structures. While early historical cities seem to indicate undeniable contraction during the early medieval period, at the same time the number of 'non-rural' settlements known from inscriptions increases dramatically. The question, then, which must be posed, concerns the *character* of urban development in early medieval India? How might it be distinguish from earlier phases of urban development in India? What different relations did cities and towns have with their hinterlands in different phases of social and urban development? Responding to European typology of M. I. Finley, Chattopadhyaya suggests that unlike European towns in the middle ages, urban settlements in India remained the seats of men of the landed classes as well as merchant interests. As far as state forms are concerned, recent research has questioned the level of centralisation which can be attributed to early historic polities like the Mauryas. Models of 'secondary state formation' and 'regional polity' have been used to suggest that the legacy of early historic polity was not a fractured and fissiparous body of vassals and petty kings but the development of important agrarian empires with regional focii.

Over the long durée, the macro-historical record shows not a contraction of economic, social and state forms, but an *expansion* of them. This has led Chattopadhyaya to suggest another paradigm for the evolution of medieval society, the expansion of what he calls 'state-society'. He means by this term a level of social development which can economically and socially support a state, as opposed to pre-state societies. The proliferation of lineages throughout early medieval India as manifestly evident in the ever growing inscriptional record, Chattopadhyaya argues, is critical evidence of this process. The task for historians, according to Chattopadhyaya, is not to assess the structures of local and supra-local polities in terms of 'centralisation and decentralisation', but to juxtapose the different processes of their formation.

According to Chattopadhyaya's paradigm, the expansion of state society can be seen at least three levels:

1. Agrarian Expansion and Peasantisation:

Economically, it entailed the 'horizontal' spread of rural agrarian settlements. Pastoralists and hunter-gatherers were incorporated into caste society. Caste formation was the chief mechanism

through which the dominant ideology of social order based on varna division was spread. Despite the ascendancy of the heterodoxies in early historic period, this process remained crucial throughout Indian history, drawing widely dispersed and originally outlying groups into an ever expanding structure.

2. Cultic Integration:

Drawing on the Work of Eschmann, Kulke and others, Chattopadhyaya suggested that religiously, this incorporation was paralleled by an integration of local, non-Hindu cults, rituals, and sacred centres into a pan-theistic supra-local structure. Typically, the mechanism of integration was through seeking affiliation with a deity or a sacred centre which had come to acquire supra-local significance.

3. Polity Formation:

We see the emergence of lineages at the peripheral nuclei of the Mauryan state and the evolution of regional polities in these areas. There is continuous development whereby pre-state societies are transformed into 'state societies' in the form of local polities, which are in turn integrated into the structures of supra-local polity.

One advantage of this paradigm is that, because it does not assume the existence of a large centralised early historic state, early medieval society can be seen not as a fragmentation of a pan-Indian social order but rather the continuing development, within expanding local and regional contexts, of processes which themselves had given rise to state and social order in early historic times.

Research Questions

This project hopes to focus develop and resolve important research questions in light of the above-going historiography in relation to the history of Vidiśā and its surrounding region. While Chattopadhyaya's model works well for the integration of peripheral and local regions into the early medieval political/social/economic order, its explanatory power is somewhat weaker when we turn to cities and regions where economic and political structures were much older, dating back to early historic times. All historiography seems to agree that these older cities typically witnessed a contraction during the post-Gupta period – while the feudalists read this decline as symptomatic of a general transformation of society into feudal structures, the post-feudalist position tends to shift our attention to the other regions and arena of urban growth. But what exactly is the nature of this urban contraction in post Gupta times? What were the factors leading to such transformations and how did older cities, both at their heyday and in later times, differ from younger urban settlements? Light may be shed on these questions by exploring how the relationship of these towns with surrounding agrarian hinterlands changed over time. Did agrarian settlements expand in the Vidiśā region after the Gupta period? Can the archaeological record tell us anything about crop cultivation and the nature of landholding?

A second dimension which needs to be taken up is the relationship of urban and rural development to the evolution and transformation of political structures in the region. In the case of Vidiśā, little is known of direct political involvement in the region after Gupta times, though there is evidence of the occasional presence of various royal dynasties. The Gurjara-Pratihāra empire, based northward in Kannauj, and later the Paramāra empire based in Dhar in western Malwa both seem to have included Vidiśā in their domains, and there seem to be building activities of both dynasties, or their affiliates, in the town and its environment. In light of this, it may be instructive to compare 9th –11th century Vidiśā with political centres like Kannauj or Dhār. It will be instructive here to review different models of state formation that have dominated the historiography – feudalist, segmentary, and processual. A number of key issues animate this historiography – relationship between emerging polities and their predecessors, relations of

central and peripheral regions within polities, and the development and nature of political and administrative structures of hierarchy within polities. In all cases, these questions are tied to specific visions of the relationship of state to 'society' – the relationship of political structure to the socio-economic order. A clear appreciation of the different evidentiary implications of each model need to be understood before research is conducted. Here a comparative framework, particularly one which includes both archaeological and historical studies in other contexts like early medieval Europe and the Mediterranean, will be helpful.

Ultimately, the refinement and resolution of these research questions needs to be driven by a strong interdisciplinary approach at all levels, at both the initial stages of question formulation, the gathering of evidence, and the refinement and resolution of questions in the context of data analysis. In general, historians have engaged with the archaeological evidence in a somewhat cursory manner. Archaeologists and historians must work together to correlate traditional textual and administrative sources – including not only inscriptions, coins and literary texts dating from this period, but later Sultanate and Mughal, and even early colonial records-- with a variety of archaeological evidence – including not only settlement archaeology, pottery sequences, but landscape surveys, and paleo botanical and hydrological evidence.

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